

DIVERSITY AND SEASONAL FLUCTUATION OF PHYTOPLANKTON IN FRESHWATER RESERVOIR KHAIRKATTA DIST, KANKER, CHHATTISGARH

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ABSTRACT

Phytoplankton are the subject of great interest because of their role as primary producers in an aquatic ecosystem. The quantitative and qualitative studies of phytoplankton may provide good indices of water quality and capacity of water to sustain heterotrophic communities. The phytoplanktonic community are 29 species of the following 4 groups: Chlorophyceae 12 Species (48.00%), Myxophyceae 9 Species (36.00%), Bacillariophyceae 3 Species (12.00%) and Euglenophyceae 1 species (4.00%) has been observed at Khairkatta Dam during study periods. The diversity of the different phytoplankton is more in summer season than during winter and rainy season.

Key words: Diversity, Density, Khairkatta

INTRODUCTION

Plankton is the most sensitive floating community which is being the first target of water pollution, thus any undesirable change in aquatic ecosystem affects diversity as well as biomass of this community. Phytoplankton are Autotrophs and belonging to first trophic level. The environmental variables such as temperature, pH and phosphate play a decisive role in altering the phytoplankton density. The diversity and seasonal fluctuation of Phytoplankton observed in Khairkatta Dam during one year study period. Similar attempts have also been made in different freshwater bodies of India: Davis C.C.(1955), Zafar A.R.(1957), Philipose M.T.(1960), Zafar (1968), Sharma A.P. (1980), Velecha V. and Bhatnagar G.P. (1988), Mahajan A.(1995), Mishra, N.K. (2005), Shanker(2010), Leela et al. (2010),

Nafeesa et al., 2011; Purushothama et al., 2011; Roy et al., 2011; Sayeswarab et al., 2011c; 2011d; 2011e.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area:

The Khairkatta fresh water reservoir is situated about 127 km west of Kanker city. Khairkatta reservoir is situated between 20.10° 32.460 N. latitude and 80.37° 22.810 E longitudes. The reservoir was surrounded by dense forest from two sides. The water spread area is 9717 hectares. Phytoplankton diversity: Site 1 was fixed at near the Mendra village, site 2 near the village P.V no 1.

Water of Dam is used for irrigation and aquaculture practices. Present work has been

conducted on two sampling sites of Khairkatta Dam for the estimation of its Grazed site remained more or less constant through the year. It ranged from 0.02 to 0.03 percent. The overall organic carbon (0.48%), the percentage of nitrogen in the soil ranged between 0.07 to 0.36% and available potassium (53 to 92 ppm).

from the reservoir was fixed with 5 percent formalin for sedimentation. This sedimented sample was observed under microscope for algal composition and diagram was drawn. The identification of phytoplankton up to the species was with the help of literature cited Philips M.T (1967) and Gandhi (1995).

The present investigation was carried out for a period of one year's January to December 2011. Biological samples have been collected

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The population of phytoplankton in Khairkatta

Figure-1. Satellite image of Khairkatta Dam

Table. 1:- Diversity of phytoplanktonic group of Khairkatta Dam Kanker C.G

Chlorophyceae	Myxophyceae	Bascillarophyceae	Euglenophyceae
Cosmarium	Anabena	Diatoma vulgare	Euglena
Chlorella	Arthrospira jeanneri	Nitzschia	
Closterium	Microcystis aeruginosa	Navicula	
Gongrosira	Merismopedia glauca		
Odogonium	Nostoc		
Pedistraum simplex	Oscillatoria		
Schroederia setigera	Stigonema		
Sphaerocystis	Scytonema		
Scandesmus arcuatus	Spirulina		
Spirogyra microspora			
Ulothrix tenuissima			
Zygnema indicum			

Figure-2. Percentage composition of Phytoplankton in Khairkatta Dam

Dam composed of four major groups namely chlorophyceae, bacillariophyceae, myxophyceae, euglenophyceae. All the dominant group of phytoplankton were present throughout the year. Diversity analysis showed that Chlorophyceae had 12 species, bacillariophyceae 03, Myxophyceae 09 species, Euglenophyceae 01 species. Their diversity of phytoplankton group show in table No. 1. Seasonal variation of phytoplanktonic species show in table No. 2. In the present investigation, the phytoplankton fluctuates monthly and its productivity high during summer season and low in winter and rainy season.

Maximum density of phytoplankton was observed at site P.V. 1 no village. %).

Table-2: Seasonal variation (%) phytoplankton in the fresh water Reservoir Khairkatta.

Season	Bacillariophyceae	Myxophyceae	Chlorophyceae	Euglenophyceae
Winter	112	86	73	14
Summer	341	32	134	23
Rainy	33	154	38	07
Total	486	272	245	44
Percentage	46.41	25.97	23.40	4.20

Figure-3. Seasonal fluctuation of phytoplankton in Khairkatta Dam

Chlorophyceae was observed to be the most dominant class of phytoplankton. Thus qualitatively Chlorophyceae formed the largest group and was followed by other group. The entire phytoplankton group was recorded throughout years.

During the study Bacillariophyceae, Chlorophyceae and Euglenophyceae were most dominated in summer and minimum observed in rainy season. Devika et al., (2006) also recorded high population during summer and suggested that this might be due to physical rather than chemical condition in which the water temperature and transparency had a direct relation with phytoplankton population. Ven Den Hoek et al., (1995) reported that higher Chlorophyceae are a large and important group of fish water algae. (%). Chlorophyceae was observed to be the most dominant class of phytoplankton. Thus qualitatively Chlorophyceae formed the largest group and was followed by other group.

CONCLUSION

The phytoplanktonic community is represented by 4 class and 25 species. Density of the different group of phytoplankton is more in the summer season than during winter and rainy season. The water of reservoir used for fish culture, Irrigation and drinking purpose.

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